

Unifying the four interactions governing the Universe, An Overview[†]

U. C. Agarwal^a and H. L. Nigam^{b*}

^aFormerly in the Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208 016, Uttar Pradesh, India

^bFormerly in the Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr_nigam@rediffmail.com, dr_nigam@sify.com

Manuscript received 01 July 2011, accepted 04 July 2011

Abstract : The nature of the matter and/or energy present in the Universe is seen as ultimate interactions in between all fundamental particles at very high energy. The forces designated as electromagnetic, strong, weak and gravitational are known to govern these interactions. The theories called Quantum Electrodynamics and Quantum Chromodynamics respectively are known to explain the electromagnetic and strong interactions. The weak interaction, indicated solely by p -decay phenomenon shows an astonishing property of violation of parity. The gravitational interaction is an extremely weak one at microscopic level, and the least understood interaction. A close connection has however been found between weak and electromagnetic interactions leading to the belief that a close connection exists between large scale Universe and microscopic scale universe. In fact, a search for a grand unified theory is on super-symmetry theory, super-string theory and M-theory proposed of late do not give a clear picture. This article gives an overview of this and discusses the underlying principles as also future challenges in this context.

Keywords : Fundamental particles, electromagnetic force, strong force, weak force, gravitational force, grand unified theory, super-symmetry theory, super-string theory, M-theory.

From the very inception of human civilization, man has been trying to solve the puzzle, "What matter is?". A hierarchy of particles with decreasing size was developed : molecule-atoms-proton-neutron-electron. Further conjectures, related to the same problem ended up into the amazing world of subatomic particles (leptons, quarks and gluons) and very high energy. A large number of such fematosized particles have been discovered but particles without interactions among them has the same meaning as having bricks without cement in the construction of a building. Consequently the present problem is to look into the nature of forces that link various types of these presently defined ultimate particles, so that one could understand a little about the nature of matter vis-a-vis energy.

Prior to discussing fundamental forces pervading in between these particles, we will summarize the present thinking about the particles.

(a) Elementary particles and their classification

All particles in the Universe can be divided into two basic categories fermions and bosons, distinguishable by their spin and quantum statistics. It is believed that at extremely high energy a first few microseconds after the big bang fermions and bosons were the same particles in nature, implying the existence of only one type of particles (building blocks).

Under the category of fermions come leptons with no internal structure and baryons composed of quarks. Bosons consist of mesons and force-carrier particles. Baryons and mesons together are called hadrons (Fig. 1). Fermions have spin multiples of $\frac{h}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{nh}{2}\right)$ while bosons have the value of their spin as (nh) . Every particle has its corresponding antiparticles whose behaviour is closely related but with opposite sign to charge and magnetic

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

*Address for Correspondence : Sneh Lok, B-332B, Sector-A, Sitapur Road Scheme, Lucknow-226 021, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Fig. 1. Basic particles.

moment. This concept is an outcome of Dirac's theory. For example, positron, antiprotons are respectively the antiparticles of electrons and protons. Although both fermions and bosons have their antiparticles, but there is a conservation law for fermions and not for bosons. Accordingly, the difference in the number of fermions and antifermions is constant, but bosons do not observe this law. Formally, one defines a fermion by a number +1 and the antifermion by (-1). It implies that fermions and antifermions are created or annihilated as pairs. Some particles are themselves their own antiparticles, e.g. antiparticles of photon is photon itself. Fermions obey Pauli's exclusion principle while bosons are governed by an opposite principle of increased probability of occupying the same quantum state and they prefer to occupy the same state of the system with the lowest possible energy.

Another property of fermions with half-units of spin angular momentum e.g. quarks and leptons, is their behaviour of spinning around their own axis. Quantum

mechanics demands that the direction of their spin is quantized.

Consequently the axis of their spin angular momentum is either parallel or antiparallel ($S_z = +\frac{1}{2}$ or $-\frac{1}{2}$) to the direction of their motion. Those fermions whose angular momentum axis is parallel to the direction of motion are called as right-handed particles and particles whose angular momentum axis is antiparallel to the direction of motion are called left-handed. They are also known to have helicity of +1 and -1 respectively. Thus, the right-handed particles are assumed to have helicity of +1 and left-handed particles as helicity of -1. Particles moving with the velocity of light e.g. photons or neutrinos, are represented by one handedness only. Thus neutrinos are called as left-handed particles with helicity of -1, while antineutrinos as right-handed particles with helicity of +1. Later in this article we will see that weak interactions which do not observe the parity conservation differ for the right-handed and left-handed particles. As a matter of fact, right-handed neutrinos do not show any weak interaction while left-handed ones do.

(b) Leptons

There are only six leptons and their corresponding six antileptons. Their properties are given in Table 1. It can be seen that leptons and anti-leptons are divided into three groups each which are known as three generations viz. (e^-, ν_e), (μ, ν_μ), (τ, ν_τ), (e, ν_e), (μ, ν_μ) and (τ, ν_τ) each generation consists of one lepton and its neutrino. Theoretical results suggest that there are only three generations possible. Heavy leptons are unstable and decay into

Table 1. Leptons and their properties

Leptons	Lepton No.	Anti-Lepton	Lepton No.	Generation	Mass (Mev/c ²)	Life time	Decay mode
e	+1	e^+	-1	e	0.511	∞	Stable
ν_e	+1	$\bar{\nu}_e$	-1		$< 10^{-5}$	∞	Stable
μ^-	+1	$\bar{\mu}^+$	-1	μ	105	3.2×10^{-6}	$\mu^- \rightarrow e^- + \bar{\nu}_e + \nu_\mu$
ν_μ^-	+1	$\bar{\nu}_\mu^+$	-1		1.7×10^{-1}	∞	Stable
τ^-	+1	$\bar{\tau}^+$	-1	τ	1784	4.9×10^{-13}	$\tau^- \rightarrow e^- + \bar{\nu}_e + \nu_\tau$ $\rightarrow \mu^- + \bar{\nu}_\mu + \nu_\tau$ $\rightarrow \pi^- + \nu_\tau$
ν_τ^-	+1	$\bar{\nu}_\tau^+$	-1		18	∞	Stable

*Mass is measured in the units of electron volts or megaelectron volts (10⁶ ev) and gigaelectron Volts (gev) = 10⁹ ev) sma $E = mc^2$ so $m = E/c^2$

their lighter lepton and a corresponding anti-neutrino. Each lepton is given a lepton number +1. The number for their corresponding lepton is -1. In the decay process of heavy leptons or any reaction, the lepton number is conserved (e.g. $\mu \rightarrow e + \bar{\nu}_e + \nu_\mu$). These are Fermi particles with $m_s = \pm \frac{1}{2}$.

(c) Quarks

These is another group of fundamental particles. Their fundamental character has been proposed because of two reasons : (i) scattering experiments utilizing high energy electrons (energy upto 100 Gev) suggested protons to contain three point like spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles with charge $-\frac{e}{3}$ and $+\frac{ie}{3}$, (ii) the existence of hundreds of different type of hadrons and that many of them decay into other hadrons. With these two experimental evidences, Gell-Mann and George Zweig in 1963 independently proposed that hadrons have elemental substructures, consisting of either two or three constituents called quarks. Originally they proposed the existence of only three different types of quarks, viz. up (u), down (d) and sharp (s), but later three more quarks, viz. charmed (c), bottoms (b) and top (t) were discovered totalling them to be six in number. These different quarks are known as their flavors. An unusual property of this is that they have fractional charges. Thus three quarks (u,c,t) have an electric charge of $+\frac{ie}{3}$, while the remaining three (d,s,b) have an electric charge of $-\frac{e}{3}$. Analogons to leptons, they have also been grouped into three generations viz. (u,d), (c,s) and (t,b). All the hadrons are composed of quarks. Thus baryon has three quarks and mesons has two quarks namely a quark and an anti-quark. Each quark has its anti-quark. Quarks are Fermi particles with spin angular momentum equal to $\frac{1}{2}$. Baryons are Fermi particles while mesons are bosons. Some of their properties are given in Tables 2 and 3. The

Table 2. Properties of quarks

Name	Bayron no	Strange-ness	Charm-ness	Bottom-ness	Top-ness	Rest Mass
Up (u)	1/3	0	0	0	0	360 mev
Down (d)	1/3	0	0	0	0	360 mev
Strange (s)	1/3	-1	0	0	0	540 mev
Charm (c)	1/3	0	-1	0	0	1500 mev
Bottom (b)	1/3	0	0	-1	0	5 Gev
Top (t)	1/3	0	0	0	-1	173 Gev

composition of all hadrons are specified by the following four rules.

(1) Mesons are composed of one quark and its anti-quark ($q \bar{q}$). Baryon number of all mesons is zero.

(2) All baryons consist of three quarks (q_1, q_2, q_3) in such a way that the total electric charge of the baryon becomes either an integral number or zero.

(3) Anti-baryons consist of three anti-quarks ($\bar{q}_1, \bar{q}_2, \bar{q}_3$) in such a way that the total charge of baryon becomes either an integral number or zero.

(4) All stable matter is formed by u and s quarks only Unstable heavy mesons and baryons are formed by the quarks of 2nd and 3rd generations. Tables 4 and 5 list the properties and composition of some mesons and baryons.

A large number of mesons containing massive quarks like top, bottom, charm etc. have been synthesized in the last decade of the 20th century. They are all unstable decaying into mesons having less massive quarks.

Experimentally quarks in all the three generation do not exist in free state and are said to be confined (see later part). The results from the nature of strong interaction does not allow the mass of quarks to be determined. All quarks carry colour charges which are of three types red (r), blue (b) and green (g).

Table 3. Properties of anti-quarks

Name	Sign	Spin	Charge	Bayron no.	Strange-ness	Charm-ness	Bottom-ness	Top-ness
Antiup	\bar{u}	$\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{2}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	0	0
Antidown	\bar{d}	$\frac{1}{2}$	$+\frac{1}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	0	0
Antistrong	\bar{s}	$\frac{1}{2}$	$+\frac{1}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	+1	0	0	0
Anticharm	\bar{c}	$\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{2}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	0	+1	0	0
Antibottom	\bar{b}	$\frac{1}{2}$	$+\frac{1}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	+1	0
Antitop	\bar{t}	$\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{2}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	0	+1

Table 4. Properties of some mesons

Particle	Spin 0			Particle	Spin 1		
	Quark comp.	Charge	Mass (Mev)		Quark comp.	Charge	Mass (Mev)
π^+	$(u\bar{d})$	+1	140	e^+	$(u\bar{d})$	+1	770
π^0	$1/\sqrt{2}(d\bar{d}-u\bar{u})$	0	135	e^0	$1/\sqrt{2}(d\bar{d}-u\bar{u})$	0	770
π^-	$(\bar{u}d)$	-1	140	e^-	$(\bar{u}d)$	-1	770
η	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(d\bar{d}-u\bar{u})$	0	549	ω	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(d\bar{d}-u\bar{u})$	0	783
K^+	$(u\bar{s})$	+1	494	K^{*+}	$(u\bar{s})$	+1	892
K^0	$(d\bar{s})$	0	498	K^{*0}	$(d\bar{s})$	0	892
K^-	$(\bar{u}s)$	-1	494	K^{*-}	$(\bar{u}s)$	-1	892
\bar{K}^0	$(\bar{d}s)$	0	498	K^{*0}	$(\bar{d}s)$	0	892
η'	$(s\bar{s})$	0	758	ϕ	$(s\bar{s})$	0	1020
J/ψ	$(c\bar{c})$	0	-				
B^+	$(u\bar{b})$	+1	5279				
B^-	$(d\bar{b})$	-1	5279				
Y	$(b\bar{b})$	0	9460				

Table 5. Properties of some bayrons

Particle	Spin 1/2			Particle	Spin 3/2		
	Quark comp.	Charge	Mass (Mev)		Quark comp.	Charge	Mass (Mev)
-	$u u u$	-	-	Δ^{++}	$u u u$	+2	1230
P	$(u u d)$	+1	938	Δ^+	$(u u d)$	+1	1231
η	$(u d d)$	0	940	Δ^0	$(u d d)$	0	1232
	$(d d d)$	-	-	Δ^-	$(d d d)$	-1	1234
Δ	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}[(ud - du)s]$	0	1116	-	-	-	-
Σ^+	$(u u s)$	1	1189	Σ^{*+}	$(u u s)$	+1	1383
Σ^0	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}[(ud - du)s]$	0	1192	Σ^{*0}	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}[(ud - du)s]$	0	1384
Σ^-	$(d d s)$	-1	1197	Σ^{*-}	$(d d s)$	-1	1387
Ξ^0	$(u s s)$	0	1318	Ξ^{*0}	$(u s s)$	0	1532
Ξ^-	$(d s s)$	-1	1321	Ξ^{*-}	$(d s s)$	-1	4535
Ω	$(s s s)$	-	-	Ω^-	$(s s s)$	-1	1672

Besides the particles described above, there exists another category of particles called "Resonances". They live for a considerably shorter time, decaying after a few particles seconds (10^{-23} sec), so that they can never travel farther than few times their size. So consequently they can not be experimentally detected and their existence can be detected and inferred only indirectly.

All the particles mentioned in the foregoing paragraphs can be created and annihilated in collision processes. Each one of the mesons can also be exchanged as a virtual

particle discussed later and thus contribute to the forces between particles with the result that there will be a vast number of different particles interactions.

The above particles can not exist in the free state without interaction. "What holds them together" is another problem. There must be some cementing material so that they can hold together and form matter in the Universe. It implies that various fundamental particles must interact among themselves. There could be an infinite number of different interactions but examining the behaviour of all

of them, they can be classified into four basic interactions. Prior to their discussion let us examine “what actually we mean by the term “Interactions”.

One can classify them into four fundamental interactions and any of the known interaction or force is merely a manifestation of one of these four basic kinds. Further more, fundamentally even these four basic types are really separate ones but can be united into one at a very large energy which is difficult to achieve so far. These four interactions are

- (i) Electromagnetic interaction/forces
- (ii) Strong interactions/forces
- (iii) Weak interactions/forces
- (iv) Gravitational interaction/forces

Classically interaction at a distance (e.g. in electromagnetism) is described in terms of potential or field due to one charged particle acting on another. The field is described as being present in the whole space around the charge. Quantum mechanically, the interaction is described in terms of an exchange interaction. In all the interactions there are some virtual particles which earn with them a part of one charged-particle’s momentum and impart it to another charged particle. The rate of exchange of the momentum determines the degree of interaction between them which becomes the measure of force. A day-to-day example of such exchange of momentum is given as follows : Suppose there are two ice skaters running side by side and exchanging a ball among each other. Internally, they are moving parallel, but at a later stage, they start diverging as if they are repelling each other. It does not imply that all exchange interaction should be repulsive in nature. One should not forget that in quantum mechanics, the carrier virtual particle (e.g. a ball in our example) does not have a classical trajectory. Further more the momentum that it carries with it from one charged particle to another is a vector quantity and therefore its value may be either positive or negative. Hence such exchange forces may either be repulsive or attractive.

Since the exchange particle or the quantum particle carries momentum and energy from one charged particle to the next, they are known as carrier bosons or gauge bosons (because they have integral spin). For example, electromagnetic radiation (light) is described classically in terms of interacting electric and magnetic fields, but quantum mechanically, it is described into terms of photons which are quanta of electromagnetic radiation. In

this manner electromagnetic interaction between two charges is described as the exchange of photons which mediate the interaction. These photons can be either created or annihilated out of the field of the charges. Analogously, all other interactions of nature are also described by the exchange of momentum carried by their respective virtual carrier or gauge bosons between two interacting particles. The name of the carrier particle along with some of their properties for each of the four interactions are given in Table 6. When two colliding charged particles approach each other (represented in the diagram by straight lines with an arrow showing direction of the particle, and move in a straight line which may be changed intermittently by exchange of a gauge boson carrying momentum Δp then each of them (both particles) has its momentum changed by an amount Δp by the exchanged boson. The gauge boson also has an energy ($C\Delta p$) which is exchanged between the charged particles. However, it is worthwhile asking the question, as from where, this energy ($C\Delta p$) is derived, because it is not available from the particles owing to the conservation of energy of the system and because the charged particles carry with them all the energy available in the interaction. This energy deficit ($C\Delta p$) which the gauge boson carries comes from the system (or vacuum) itself because of the uncertainty relationship ($\Delta E \cdot \Delta t \leq h/2\pi$ or $\Delta p \cdot \Delta x \leq h/2\pi$). It says that a particle (quantum particle) which is observed during a short time, Δt has indeterminate energy fluctuations upto ΔE , above the total energy of the system permitted by the conservation of energy. The extra energy of the two colliding systems ($\Delta E \approx C\Delta p$) can accordingly exist for a short time Δt . Or if the boson particle is moving with a velocity C , it can travel to a maximum distance (Δt), which is defined as the range of interaction. After this time $\Delta t = \left(\frac{h}{2\pi \cdot \Delta E} \right)$, the extra energy ($C\Delta p$) has to be returned to the system. This extra energy ($\Delta E \approx C\Delta p$) and thus the range of interaction will depend upon the mass of the boson particle. However, for the boson particle the range is shorter. Therefore, bosons with zero mass like photon or gluon particles have infinite range of interaction. Further, it is not possible to observe these virtual boson particles directly with the help of any experiment. Therefore these boson particles are termed as virtual bosons. They are hidden in the intermediate haze which prevails when in microcosmos, one particle looks at another particle. Their range is given in Table 6.

Table 6. Fundamental interaction carrier particles and their properties ($MC^2 = 1 \text{ GeV}$)

Interaction	Gravitational	Electromagnetic	Weak	Strong
Properties				
Field boson	Graviton	Photon	W^\pm, Z^0	Gluons
Spin parity	2^+	1^-	$1^-, 1^+$	1
Mass (Gev)	0	0	$M_W = 80.2, M_Z = 91.2$	0
Range and source	∞ mass	∞ Electric charge	10^{-18} m weak charge	$\leq 10^{-15}$ m colour charge
Coupling constant (α)	$\frac{G_N M^2}{4\pi\hbar c} = \alpha_G$	$\alpha = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c}$	$\frac{G(MC^2)^2}{(\hbar c)^3}$	$\alpha_s \leq 1$
Typical cross section	5×10^{-40}	$1/137$	1.17×10^{-5}	10^{-30}
Typical life time	-	10^{-33}	10^{-39}	10^{-23}
Relation strength	10^{-36}	1	10^{-7}	20
Symbol for representation in Feynman diagram	-			

The theory which explains all the phenomena of electromagnetic interactions is known as Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), perfected by Feynman, Schwinger and Tomonago. Feynman simplified the complicated mathematical theory (QED) by displaying the interactions between the particles in a graphical way by space-time diagram for one boson exchange (Fig. 2). It should be kept in mind that at quantum level, the interaction between two passing charges is not a one-step process. In the individual interactions, the vital parameter is the strength of coupling between the carrier boson and the charge of the particle. The coupling is given by the term, α which is a dimensionless quantity given by the expression $\frac{(\text{Charge})^2}{4\pi E_{0\hbar c}}$. Their values are given in Table 6.

It must also be remembered that in these types of interactions, Newtonian continuous forces between two charges are described by a continual "package" transfer in the form of a field quantity, viz. gauge boson. Further every quantum event has quantum uncertainties. The production of quantum boson particles, their emission and absorptions are uncertain. It is also uncertain where and when these events will occur. Newtonian determinism has been replaced by a probabilistic law. Charged par-

ticle means that it has the ability to emit and absorb photons. It also replaces a continuous path of the particles by a jerky non-deterministic path. However, the low energy bosons predict a fairly smooth path, while the high energy ones by the non-Newtonians ones (Fig. 4).

We would also like to point out that during these interactions certain equations pertaining to electromagnetic or other interactions remain invariant. These can be described by the so called "Gauge Invariances". Wherever there are such invariances, the accounting system of field theory reveals energy transfer which leads to forces. Thus, forces are Nature's way of preserving such underlying invariances as these lead to forces. We will not discuss this theory here, but we would like to point out that transformation leads to invariances which subsequently leads to forces.

The interaction of particles are responsible for the scattering and transformation (decays and reaction). An isolated particle may decay into other particles. In case the interaction of two particles results in the production of the same particles, then the scattering is elastic scattering. In case, it leads to different particles, the scattering is "Inelastic".

Fig. 2. Feynman diagram for electromagnetic interaction.

Electromagnetic interactions

The concept of force field was given by Faraday. It was long known that the strength of the electromagnetic force is universally proportional to the square of distance between the charges and directly proportional to the product of the sizes of charges q_1 and q_2 . Electric charge exists in two varieties, positive and negative and the forces can be attractive and repulsive (same charges repel and opposite charges attract). In order to provide the directional quality to forces, Faraday gave the concept of the lines of force emanating from the charges from which he calculated the strength of the electric field, E and the magnetic field, B . The equations that underly these calculations in space-time are important characterization of force between the charges. The laws that describe separate electric and magnetic forces due to stationary electric and magnet charges are, however, not fundamental. These are a part of a larger picture because moving electric charges produce magnetic effects and moving magnets produce electric effects. The above two forces are synthesized by James Clark Maxwell into his four equations describing the overall electromagnetic force field. These were further linked with light. These forces hold the at-

oms together and describe the physical properties of matter in bulk like m.p., b.p., compressibility, elasticity etc. These are responsible for all the chemical reactions which allow atoms to combine in millions of varieties of ways. In any atom, the total negative charge balances the total positive charges so that the atom is overall neutral. Despite balancing of (+ve) and (-ve) charge in an atom, the atoms combine together to form molecules by the residual electromagnetic forces/charge.

Consequently various type of bonds ionic, covalent etc. are formed. These forces between atoms and molecules are also responsible for the bulk force like frictional force.

The discussion in the proceeding paragraph described the electromagnetic force in a classical way. These method are not sufficient to explain the detailed interaction and even to described the way the atoms absorb and emit radiation. These have to be explained by relatively new theory called QED. According to this, the electric charges are still the source of electromagnetic field which is grainy in nature and quantized. As we have discussed earlier, if we look closely enough, we would see that the field around the charge is due to tiny field quantum particles called

virtual photons that are consequently emitting out and absorbing in the field like the bees in a beehive. Farther from the charge, the field becomes weak because the photon becomes more spread out. These photons are packets of energy and momentum and transfer energy from one field to another. Thus when two charges approach towards each other, their respective swarms of virtual photons start to overlap. This provides an alternate destination to be absorbed and they forget their parent charge field or charge. Rather than returning to their parent charge fields, the virtual photons give their energy and momentum to the second electron field. Thus momentum transfer or transaction between two charge is felt as force. In this fashion, virtual photons act as carrier particles for the electromagnetic field interaction. These particles have a very short existence $\Delta t = \frac{h}{2\pi \Delta e}$. In this manner, the QED treats interactions between the electric charge particles in terms of the exchange of virtual photons. The strength of these electromagnetic interactions is given by the numerical value of the coupling constant, α , which equals to 1/137.

Consider what happens when a real electron is embedded in the clouds of virtual photons. These virtual photons, at times will be transforming into virtual electron-positron pairs. Although virtual photons do not have any effect on the charge particles (or electrons); but the virtual electrons will polarize the real electrons present on the charged particles. This results in the shielding of the charge and thereby reducing the negative charge on the real electron, greater than the charge measured on the particles experimentally. In QED bare charge is assumed to be infinite while the measured charge is assumed to be residual charge which remained after shielding. Since α is proportional to the quantity of charge on the electron, the value of coupling constant, α will vary with the distance at which the interaction is being measured between the two charges. The value 1/137 is observed at 10 cm. However in any event the law of conservation of charge is strictly observed at all the distances (Fig. 3).

Strong interactions

Referring to the earlier part of the article, all hadrons are composed of quarks. Baryons have three quarks (q_1, q_2, q_3) while mesons have one quark and its anti-quark (q_1, \bar{q}_1). The structures of baryons having three quarks posed a problem in regards to the Pauli exclusion principle. For example, Δ baryon has a spin of 3/2 [$(u \uparrow u \uparrow u \uparrow)$]. The $(3/2) \Delta$ is characterized by the symmetric

wave function of the three quarks ($\psi_u \psi_u \psi_u$) if spin and space parts of the wave functions are assumed to be symmetric. Baryon being a Fermi particle, should have asymmetric wave function in its ground state and therefore the symmetric wave function violates the Pauli principle. The solution of this puzzle was sought by assuming another degree of freedom viz. colour for the quarks. It has been assumed that quarks exist in three colours – red, (r), blue (b) and green (g) and the net colour which a baryon or a meson could have must be zero (or white). These three colours of any quarks signify the “Strong Charge” of the quarks similar to positive and negative charge on a particle. We will further see that the gauge boson particle in the case of strong interaction which mediates the strong force between quarks are gluons similar to photons in electromagnetic interaction. The prevailing theory is called as Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD). Chromo signifies the colour charge on the quarks responsible for strong forces. Contrary to photons, gluons also have colour charges. The coupling constant between two colour charges is proportional to the product of colour charges. The particles having no colour charge (white particle) are not subjected to strong force. The strong force coupling constant is numerically larger than that of electromagnetic forces. One can imagine the repulsive force between two quarks to be 10^9 times more intense than between an outer-electron and the nucleus in an atom. Still the quarks are together. It indicates the strength of strong colour interaction in relation to electric forces.

Quarks are held together by colour forces. It has been assumed that quarks with different colours attract each other while with same colours repel each other. Two colourless hadrons (e.g. neutron and proton) feel practically no colour force. But if two colourless hadrons come close together, the coloured quarks in each hadrons may feel a little colour force from the quarks in the other hadron. This effect is called the residual interaction similar to Van der Waal's forces among molecules. This residual interaction is responsible for a variety of nuclear phenomena e.g. ($n-n$), ($n-p$) or ($p-p$) attraction in atomic nucleus and the presence of magnetic moment in neutrons, though neutron ($u d d$) has zero electric charge. Which results from a combination of magnetic moments of three quarks.

Strong force between quarks is mediated by gluons which are supposed to be massless with a spin of one. The property that makes gluons different from photons is that they unlike photons carry colour charges, but no electric charges. Consequently they interact among each

Fig. 3. Feynman diagrams of some interactions

Fig. 4. Interaction between two electrons.

other also besides that, with quarks via strong interaction. In this manner gluons produce more gluons. Consequently when two quarks are being separated, gluons pull on each other with more force because gluons being coloured start emitting more gluons. It is also not possible to separate an individual gluon like an individual quark. Nonetheless strong indirect evidences have been obtained for the existence of gluons. Gluons similar to mesons are eight in number (Table 4). These are : (r b), (r g), (b g), (b r), (g r), (g b), g_1 and g_2 . Just as electromagnetic field is coupled with photons (photons are created and absorbed by the field), the density and the current of a conserved quantity, charge, the gluon field is coupled to colour by a coupling constant, α . This coupling constant α , is effectively larger at large interquark distance (r) and becomes infinite at a certain distance (r_c). At smaller distances, the effective coupling α , becomes very small (asymptotic freedom). Thus, despite gluons being massless the range of strong force is small (less than 10 m). Once a quark and an anti-quark combine to form hadron. They cannot be separated. This property is called "Confinement".

Referring to the above description, the mechanism of strong force transmission is similar to that of electromagnetism. The interaction between the charged particle is described as the exchange of a gauge boson (a momentum Δp), viz. gluons which are massless particles and are eight in number. Some of the gluons carry colour charges which alter the character of the strong force. They can change the colour of quark (Fig. 5).

As mediators of strong interactions gluons can not change the flavour of a quark. Thus the only allowed quark and gluon interactions are of the form : $q g \rightarrow q g$, $q g \rightarrow q g$, $q q \rightarrow g$ or $g \rightarrow q g$ or their charge conjugates. Here quarks must be of the same flavour (Here $q =$

quark and $g =$ gluon) (Fig. 5). In all these interactions the colour is conserved because gluons carry colours. The colour of the quark is changed. Colour change between quarks in hadrons requires that all mesons and baryons involved in the interaction remain colourless prior to or post-interaction, e.g. $p + \pi^0 \rightarrow \pi^0 + \Delta$.

The probability of two colliding hadrons to undergo reaction or interaction – to interact with one another depends on the energy involved in collision.

Sometimes in some reaction at certain value of energy, the probability of the reaction increases sharply. It means that the reaction is much more likely to occur at this particular energy value with the formation of a short lived intermediate hadron with a mass corresponding to the energy at which the increase is observed. These intermediate hadrons are the 'resonances' formed by the strong interactions between different hadrons.

As more and more of particles are discovered, it is realized that it is highly unsatisfactory to associate each particle with a fundamental field. The framework, which seems most appropriate for the description of hadron reactions interactions is called "S-matrix theory" originally proposed by Heisenberg in 1943. Here one is concerned not with the groups of objects (particles), but with the groups of connections. Here we divide the Universe in a certain tissue of events in which connections (relationship among different events, rather than particles) of different kinds overlap or combine and thereby determine the texture of the Universe.

The "S-matrix theory" is still not well developed. Since it is highly complex and mathematical, we will not deal with this theory. However, it is important to know that in this theory, particle does not play any major role in the description of events. It is the events themselves which are important.

Fig. 5 and 6. Simple gluon exchange interaction between quarks and between quarks and \bar{q} (anti-quark)

Weak interactions

The weak interaction is the most obscure out of the four interactions. One feels the presence of gravitational and the electromagnetic interactions all the time because of their long range. The presence of nuclei in all the atoms shows the presence of strong interaction. But somehow weak interaction is very elusive, possibly because of its very short range and its absence in day to day events (range < 10 m). It is 10^{12} times weaker than the electromagnetic and 10^{23} times stronger than the gravitational interaction. The only observed example which indicates its presence is the β -decay phenomenon.

One can view the particle decays and many other reactions in terms of the fundamental particles and their relevant interactions. For example, one considers the decay of neutrons in terms of the quark components of neutrons and protons. The decay suggests the manner in which

weak interaction acts on quarks and on leptons. It can transform a lepton to a neutrino or vice versa, but only within the same generation. It can change the flavour of a quark through their weak force carrier bosons viz. w whereby it changes a quark to V^- , quark (or vice versa). Analogous transformation occurs in anti-quarks (Fig. 7)

Fig. 7. $n \rightarrow p$ transformation

An interacting example of a decay process whereby W^+ force carrier bosons couple two quarks and two flavour changes take place simultaneously (Fig. 8) is given by the following decay process : In the example of neutron decay (Fig. 7), there is no mixing of quark generation ($d \rightarrow u$), but the decay of $k^- \rightarrow u^- + \bar{\nu}_\mu$ is an example of quark generation mixing. Although the process of mixing of generation is prohibited, but Cabbalas gave a mechanism whereby generation mixing could be a possible decay mode.

Fig. 8. $D^0 \rightarrow K^- + e^- + \bar{\nu}_e$ transformation.

The importance of weak force in nature is shown by the fact that if weak force would not have been there, there would not have been any life on earth. The weakness of weak force prevents our Sun (or in general all stars) from collapsing since β -decay process is an extremely necessary first step in the burning of hydrogen. Most of the energy from the Sun is provided through the conversion of hydrogen to helium in which the first step is the weak interaction between two protons forming deuterium. The reactions are as follows :

- (i) $p + p \rightarrow d + e^+ + \gamma \dots\dots\dots$
Weak interaction (1st step)
- (ii) $d + p \rightarrow {}^3\text{He} + \gamma \dots\dots\dots$ 2nd step
- (iii) ${}^3\text{He} + {}^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}^4\text{He} + p + p \dots\dots\dots$ 3rd step

The first step is a weak interaction process since only weak interaction can give rise to positron which is necessary to conserve charge in fusion of two protons together to give deuterium. This fusion reaction is taking place in the core of the Sun where the temperature is high enough

for such a fusion reaction.

There are examples of weak interaction by which the charges of interacting particles are not changed (Fig. 9). Thus we can classify weak interactions into two categories; (a) Weak interactions mediated by charged boson particle (W) in which charges on the interacting particles are changed. There are called charged current weak interaction (Figs. 7 and 8). (b) Weak interaction which are mediated by neutral boson particles (Z^0) in which charges of the interacting particles are not transferred from one particles to another. Such interactions are termed as Neutral current weak interactions (Fig. 9).

Weak interactions take place between all types of leptons and quarks. These can transform the flavours of quarks from one lepton to another in the same generations. Some times the generation of the particles are also changed through a different mechanism. Thus taking the example of particles of first generation leptons viz. $\begin{pmatrix} e^- \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} e^+ \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}$ and first generation quarks, viz. $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ d \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u} \\ \bar{d} \end{pmatrix}$ the total number of particles will be thirty as shown below :

		Total particle
Leptons (1st generation)	$\begin{pmatrix} e \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} e^+ \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 2\text{L-H} \\ 1\text{L-H} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 2\text{R-H} \\ 1\text{R-H} \end{pmatrix}$ (2 particles) + (2 anti-particles) \rightarrow (3 particles) + (3 anti-particles)	6
Quarks (1st generation)	$\begin{pmatrix} u_R u_B u_G \\ d_R d_B d_G \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_R \bar{u}_B \bar{u}_G \\ \bar{d}_R \bar{d}_B \bar{d}_G \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow$ Their R-H and L-H components of particles	24
Total		30

(R, B, G, R-H, L-H stands respectively for red, blue, green, right-handed and left-handed)

Fig. 9. Weak interactions in which carrier particles are Z^0 (chargeless bosons).

It parity is conserved by weak interactions, all the thirty particles should observe this conservation law. It was shown by Lea and Yong in 1956 that parity in weak interaction is not conserved. Consequently the left-handed and right-handed particles interact differently. Weak interaction are associated with weak charge (i) defined by a weak dimensionless coupling constant a_w . This weak charge (i) unlike other charges, has the universal property of being associated on the basis of handedness. Thus weak charge is assumed to be present only on the left-handed particles and right-handed anti-particles. It is assumed to be zero on right-handed particles and left-handed anti-particles. That is they are neutral particles and do not participate in weak interactions. Consequently unlike other changes, weak charges are not conserved in weak interactions. Its value depends upon the direction of the motion of the particle and it charges with the change of its motion. It is only in that case when the particle becomes massless, the charges are conserved and handedness of the particles disappears.

The second unusual behaviour of weak interactions is that it acts only on doublets [viz. $\begin{pmatrix} e^- \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} e^+ \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u \\ d \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u \\ d \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \mu^- \\ \nu_\mu \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \mu^+ \\ \nu_\mu \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \tau^- \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \tau^+ \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix} \dots \dots \text{etc.}$]. In these doublets one member is assigned a charge of $+ \frac{1}{2}$ and the other, $-\frac{1}{2}$, e.g. $\begin{pmatrix} +\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$. These doublets are given in Fig. 10.

of (+ 1); w^- having a weak charge and an electric charge of (-1) and z , with weak and electric charge of (0,0) The z particle, like photons and gluons convey the weak force by weak interactions between particles having weak charges but the characteristics of the interacting particles are not perturbed (Fig. 9). W^+ and w^- change the flavours of the particles e.g. $u \rightarrow d$ or vice versa. For example, when w particle is emitted from the field of electron with weak charge of $(-\frac{1}{2})$ and electric charge of (-1) , it is transformed to ν_e having weak charge of $(-\frac{1}{2})$ and electric charge of zero. Similarly by the emission of w^+ , d quark with weak and electric charge equal to $(-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$ is transformed to u quark with weak and electric charge equal to $+\frac{1}{2}$ and $+\frac{2}{3}$, respectively. Furthermore, it is noteworthy to note that for the carrier particles, w^\pm, z^0 , both weak and electric charges are whole numbers. As noted earlier, weak interactions come in two categories; (a) charge current weak interaction mediated by w^* and (b) neutral current weak interaction mediate by z^0 particles (Fig. 9). One may also have transformation by weak interactions in doublets like $(\nu_e, e^-), (u, d^-), (c, s^-), (t, b^-)$ where d^-, s^- and b^- are certain linear combinations of (d, s, b) . The exchange of w^\pm changes flavours while that of z^0 conserves flavours.

Gravitational interactions

It is nature's fourth fundamental interaction which is still not well understood at microscopic level despite its being fully known for macroscopic level. It is very hard to work out a theory of gravitation in the form of the

$\begin{pmatrix} e^- \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u_{LH} \\ d_{LH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u_{RH} \\ d_{RH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u_{RH} \\ d_{RH} \end{pmatrix}$ R G B	$\xrightarrow{\text{Weak Charge}}$	$\begin{pmatrix} +\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} e_{RH}^- \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u_{RH} \\ d_{RH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u_{RH} \\ d_{RH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u_{RH} \\ d_{RH} \end{pmatrix}$ R G B	$\xrightarrow{\text{Weak Charge}}$	Zero
$\begin{pmatrix} e^+ \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_{RH} \\ \bar{d}_{RH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_{RH} \\ \bar{d}_{RH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_{RH} \\ \bar{d}_{RH} \end{pmatrix}$ R G B	$\xrightarrow{\text{Weak Charge}}$	$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} \\ +\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} e_{LH}^+ \\ \nu_e \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_{LH} \\ \bar{d}_{LH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_{LH} \\ \bar{d}_{LH} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_{LH} \\ \bar{d}_{LH} \end{pmatrix}$ R G B	$\xrightarrow{\text{Weak Charge}}$	Zero

Fig. 10. Weak charge on doublets and singlets (symbols weaning are given above).

The particles within a doublet interact among each other via weak interactions. The force carrier boson particles are w^+ having a weak charge and an electric charge

above interactions because so little is known about it at microscopic level. This interaction is extremely weak interaction. For example the gravitational attraction between

a proton and an electron is 10^{30} times weaker than the electromagnetic interaction between them. It is only then, when there is a very large concentration of matter at a macroscopic level, the gravitational effect is observed and the gravity dominates over other forces. Einstein's theory of general relativity appears to be correct at macroscopic-scale. It is a field theory and the field is defined as the space-time curvature caused by the masses of the particles. To quantize these fields is extremely difficult to do in any logical and consistent manner. However a carrier particle for the gravitational interaction has been proposed. It is termed as "Graviton". It is similar to photon, having zero mass, zero charge, moving with velocity of light and thus having infinite range. But still gravitons have not been experimentally observed. Thus even if a single proton absorbs a graviton, its recoil is so small that one can not experimentally observe it.

Unification of weak and electromagnetic interactions

In 1967 Adbus Salam and Steven Weinberg working independently found a close connection between weak and electromagnetic interactions. They proposed a new quantum field theory called Electro-weak theory. Let us recall that QED describes the electromagnetic interaction which occurs via photon mediator particles by exchanging between interacting particles. According to electro-weak theory, electrons, positrons, neutrons and anti-neutrons interact among themselves via exchange of certain other particles. These force-carrier particles include massless photons and three other particles viz. w^+ , w^- and z^0 having masses equal to about 100 times that of proton. These are similar to photons, which have (reasons unknown) acquired mass. Accordingly the weak and electromagnetic interactions are really the same type of interactions. They appear to be different because the weak exchange particles (w^+ , w^- , z^0) have mass while that of electromagnetic interactions (photon) do not have mass. Furthermore, two of the particles w^+ and w^- have charges while photon is neutral. The existence of neutral z^0 particle with mass has been experimentally verified. Higgs has proposed a new scalar particle called 'Higgs particle' created by 'Higgs field' which imparts mass to these particles i.e. weak force carrier. We do not think it appropriate to discuss Higgs theory at the place. Similar to electrons and ν_e , muons (μ^+ , μ^-), (ν_μ , $\bar{\nu}_\mu$), (τ^+ , τ^-) and (ν_τ , $\bar{\nu}_\tau$) also interact weakly via these Force-carriers (w , w , z^0). These interactions indicate a close connection between large scale universe and microscopic scale uni-

verse. Second and third generation particles are unstable and soon vanish after they are created. They played an important role during the early seconds of the Big Bang.

Search for a unified grand theory is on. Presently the efforts to unify the electro-weak theory with strong interactions and subsequently unifying with gravitational interactions. We know that second and the third generation quarks consists of two quarks in each generation. These quarks are heavier and short-lived copies of u and d quarks. These are analogous to the second and third generation leptons. The resemblance is striking and suggests that there ought to be close connection between electro-weak and strong interactions. They believe that there should be a "Grand Unified Theory" which would view the two interactions viz. electro-weak and strong as the two facets of a single underlying interaction on which work is still going on.

As a result of the attempts of unifications of forces into a single theory, a sort of a marriage between high energy microscopic and macrophysics (Astrophysics in particular) seems to be appearing at the horizon. Inner space and outer space appear to be interconnected. This union has stimulated some new remarkable ideas. Thus nature's fundamental constants viz. velocity of light, Planck's constant and gravitational constant can be combined in a certain way to obtain nature's new units of length time and energy called Planck's Scale.

Planck's length $\approx 10^{-33}$ m

Planck's time $\approx 10^{-43}$ sec

Planck's energy $\approx 10^{-23}$ J

These units were interpreted in the light of general relativity and uncertainty principal by John Wheeler equal to electromagnetic force. At still higher energies, the electro-weak interaction attains a strength that is approximately equal to strong force. It will be interesting to know that still at higher energy, viz. Planck's energy, there is a possibility to attain a strength of gravity that is roughly equal to that of strong force. It seems to be strange, because we know that gravity is a very weak interaction. But at higher energies and at shorter separation of nearly equal to that of Planck's distance (10^{-33} m), gravity becomes very strong. Thus it is anticipated that in the initially very hot universe (10^{32} degree K), all the four interactions were physically united as a single unified force. It implies that all interactions have the same symmetry. On cooling, first gravitational interaction has frozen out

of the unified interaction. It has lost symmetry that has unified gravity with the other interactions. As the universe cooled further, strong interaction separated out to form its own pattern and the symmetry was further broken. Lastly on further cooling, weak force froze out and the symmetry is further broken. Thus cooling of the universe resulted in the breaking of symmetry of the whole universe. It resulted in having four different types of interactions which are interactions at very high energy.

Super-symmetry theory

Although the standard model discussed in the preceding paragraphs is the most complete theory developed so far and it has withstood all the experimental tests performed but it does not give all the answers. For example, the particles in the standard model are classified into three generations, but only one generation (m, d, u, e, ν_e) is needed to construct our universe, (why?). The model has no answer. The model describes clearly the way the particles (Fermions) and the forces (Bosons) shape our universe. It also unifies electromagnetic and weak forces but other forces are left out. A research for other possibilities led Glashow and Georgi to think of unification in terms of super-symmetry proposed in 1971.

Super-symmetry introduces a new gauge theory which could unify quarks and leptons (matter particles) or fermions with mass-carrying particles (Boson) that carry forces. Thus it would be possible to bring together all the quantum particles as components of a single master superfield. Basically, it is an extension of standard model.

According to super-symmetry model, new dimensions are added to space that behave like fermions of spin $\frac{1}{2}$. When one pushes any fermion of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ (e.g. quark) with one of the added dimension, the added fermions is transformed to a squark of 0 or a boson. Or when one pushes a boson of spin 1 (e.g. photon) into the same dimension of space, it is transformed to a photon which is a fermion particle of spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Thus if our model of super-symmetry is correct and super-symmetry exists in nature, all the particles of nature must be present in pairs which may be termed super-particles whose spins are half a unit apart. In other words, all the three non-gravitational forces can be unified by doubling the standard model particles. We do not have yet any proof for the existence of such super-particles. Also it does not take into consideration the gravitational force.

Super-string model

One of the developments in this field is the concept of

highly mathematical super-string theory. The turgid mathematical structure of super-string theory can be simplified if more than four dimensions (x, y, z, t) are introduced in the mathematical structure. It is possible to conjecture introduction of eleven dimensions (ten space dimensions plus one time dimension), only four dimensions being observable. Basically, the conjecture of presence of higher dimension is not new. It has already been shown by Kaluza (1929) that Einstein's gravitational field equations can be generalized to five dimensional space-time. It has also been shown that electromagnetism in the context of Kaluza's theory is form of gravity, the gravity of unseen additional dimensions.

Besides many interpretations of extra further dimensions one can also picture it as a big pipeline seen from a great distance where it appears as a wiggly line and not a two or three dimensional pipe. Further in 1960, Gabriello Veneziano at CERN proposed a mathematical model to explain the existence of very short lined hadrons which explained the quantized motion of subatomic particles. On various modifications this theory led to the proposed of super-string theory by Green and Schwarz in 1984.

According to this theory, all elementary particles are represented by strings no longer than 10^{-35} m which are 10^{20} times smaller than the size of a proton. These strings can vibrate like a guitar string (standing waves). They can thus have millions of vibrational modes. Each of these vibrational modes corresponds to a particular energy of the particle (quantization of energy of a particle) and therefore the mass of a particle ($E = mc^2$), each vibrational mode is an identification of a particle and all the properties like charge, spin. These are open as well as closed strings, the quantities like electric charge or colour charge are attached to the end-points.

In the light of above properties of Green and Schwarz strings, an attempt was made to verify all the physics in one single sweep. It was soon realized that super-symmetry could be incorporated in the super-string theory in five different ways where by five different versions of super-string theory appeared which are termed as Type I, Type IIA, Type IIB, Heterotic O and Heterotic E eventually four versions were found to be faulty and only one version was supreme as a theory of all physics.

The M-theory

In 1995, Edward Witten proposed M-theory on which further work was carried out by Joseph Polchinski of the

University of California, Santa Barbera. He showed that M-theory includes objects of higher dimensions than the original two-dimensional strings. He found that the motion of the end points of these strings are free to move in all dimensions and describe two-dimensional space which is a type of membrane. These surfaces are a new type of mathematical objects within M-theory.

The dimensions of membranes can take value as large as TEN. They have their own properties, for example, charge which gives rise to electromagnetic field or Young-Mills charged force carriers. Closed chain strings can not be attached and might exist in full 11-dimensional space. Gravitation can be associated with closed strings as M-theory shows that gravity acts throughout all space. According to M-theory, photons, carriers of electromagnetic force are open-ended strings vibrations and are free to move in three dimensional spaces. M-theory seems to be correct as we will be able to see eleven dimensions through gravity. Here M-stands for Membranes, Mother of all strings, Magic, Matrix, Mystery. The M-theory is highly mathematical and it is not intended to go into details. However, it is felt that theory which produces a standard model is still far from sight.

A large number of new particles have been produced from various theories. These are fanefully named like steptons, squarks, axions, winos, photinos, zinos, glunos, etc. We can work through the vast number of unifying theories only through experimental evidence which is eluding us.

References for further reading and information

1. R. M. Barnett *et al.*, "The Charm of Strange Quarks", Springe-Verlag, New York, Donald H, Perkin, A. P. Press,

- 2000.
2. "Interaction to High Energy Physics". 4th ed., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1990.
3. Fayyazuddin and Riazuddin, "A Modern Interaction to Particle Physics", 2nd ed., World Scientific Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., Singapore, 2000.
4. K. Gottfried and V. F. Weisskopf, "Concept of Particle Physics", Vol. II, Revised ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
5. P. D. B. Collins *et al.*, "Particle Physics and Cosmology", A Wiley-Interscience Publication, New York, 1999.
6. Sheldon L. Glashow, "The Charm of Physics", American Institute of Physics, New York, 1991.
7. M. Veltman, "Facts and Mysteries in Particle Physics", World Scientific Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., New Jersey, USA, 2003.
8. L. B. Okun, " α , β , γ , Z, A Primer in Particle Physics", Harwood Academic Publisher, London, UK, 1987.
9. Nambu Y. Quarks, "Frontiers in Elementary Particle Physics", World Scientific Publishers Co. Ltd., Singapore, 1985.
10. Weinberg Steven, "United Theories of Elementary Particle Interactions", Scientific American Volume 231, 1974, pp. 50-59.
11. Kullander Sven and Larsson Borge, "Out of Sight from Quarks to Long Cells", Cambridge University Press, 1993.
12. Weinberg Steven, "The Discovery of Subatomic Particles", Scientific American Library, 1993.
13. Davies Paul, "Forces of Nature", Cambrige University Press, 1986.
14. Abdus Salam, "Unification of Fundamental Forces. The Fist of Dirac Memorial Lectures (1988)", Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge, 1988.
15. Len Kurzawan, "The Fundamental Forces, How the Universe Works", Trafford Publishing, 2009.
16. Zwieback Barton, "First Course in String Theory", Cambrige University Press, 1988.
17. Stephen Hawkins and Mlodinon, "Dreat Design", Benton Books, New York, 2010.